

DEVELOPMENT AND UTILIZATION OF THE PURWAREJA KLAMPOK- BANJARNEGARA RAILWAY LINE DURING THE DUTCH COLONIAL PERIOD, 1898-1942

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Abstract

Banjarnegara is an area in the Banyumas Residency that is crossed by a railway line. The line was built during the Dutch colonial period. Traces of this line can still be seen today. This is why this research needs to be conducted, namely to find out (a) How was the railway line through Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara built? (b) How was the Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara railway line used? (c) What was the fate of the Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara line during the Dutch colonial period? This research was conducted using historical research methods. Historical research methods consist of several stages, namely topic selection, heuristics, verification, interpretation, and historiography. The results of this research are as follows: (a) The Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara line was part of a line operated by the Serajoedal Stoomtram Maatschappij company, which was built in 1895 and completed in 1988. (b) The Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara line was used to transport industrial products, goods, and people, or for public transportation. (c) The Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara line ended with various problems, namely the Malaise and the Dutch East Indies occupation by Japan. Thus, the history of railways in Banjarnegara once had its heyday. In addition, the use of rail transportation was also quite important in supporting transportation modes in the region, boosting the community's economy, and contributing to national development efforts

Keywords: *Banjarnegara, Purwareja Klampok, SDS, trains*

INTRODUCTION

Trains are a popular form of land transportation for Indonesians, especially on the islands of Java and Sumatra. This mode of transportation is preferred because it has relatively spacious carriages that can accommodate and transport large numbers of passengers or goods (Arkaan, Yunianto, & Kurniawan, 2022:96). Railway lines that pass through rural areas and mountains are another attraction for passengers who enjoy natural beauty. The first railway in Indonesia appeared in the 19th century, when it was still Dutch East Indies. Specifically, on June 17, 1864, in Keminjen Village, East Semarang, the Semarang-Vorstenlanden line was built under the command of Governor General Mr. L.A.J Baron Sloet van de Beele (Kementerian Perhubungan, 2020:3). The construction of the railway line aimed to modernize transportation in the Dutch East Indies at that time. The need for faster and safer transportation prompted the Dutch colonial government to build railway lines in the Dutch East Indies. Railways continued to develop during the Japanese occupation and the republican era. Over time, the development of railways in Indonesia has also advanced. Changes in railway management from the early 2010s to the present have shown improvements in management, making railway users more comfortable using this mode of transportation. Therefore, railways still hold a place for their enthusiasts.

The development of railways in Indonesia has also had an impact on the government's efforts to expand the existing railway network. The government has begun constructing new lines and reactivating abandoned railway lines. One of the lines to be reactivated is the Purwokerto-Wonosobo line. As reported by *suaramerdeka.com*, a study on the reactivation of the Purwokerto-Wonosobo railway line has been conducted and construction will begin in 2030 (Soekendro, 2024). This news is certainly good news for the communities whose areas are traversed by this line. One of the areas passed by the Purwokerto-Wonosobo route is Banjarnegara Regency. Banjarnegara is one of the regions in Central Java Province. It is bordered by Pekalongan and Batang to the north, Wonosobo to the east, Kebumen to the south, and Purbalingga and Banyumas to the west. Its proximity to Banyumas and Wonosobo means

that the railway line must cross Banjarnegara. The line enters through Purwareja Klampok District and continues on to Banjarnegara. Evidence of the existence of a railroad line passing through Banjarnegara can be seen in the remains of railroad tracks that are still visible when traveling along the Ajibarang-Secang Road from Purwareja Klampok to Banjarnegara. The tracks are located on the west side of the Ajibarang-Secang Road. This indicates that the tracks were once part of the railroad system in Indonesia. The line has now largely disappeared and is mostly no longer visible. The community has begun to forget that there was once a railroad that passed through Banjarnegara. The existence of a railroad in the Banjarnegara region is now just history. There are not many references that specifically discuss this railroad, which was once prosperous in its heyday. The people living around the railway line have changed generations without leaving any written accounts that today's youth can learn from about the railway line that passed through Purwareja Klampok to Banjarnegara. For this reason, there is a need for historiography about the existence of the Purwareja Klampok - Banjarnegara railway line. The goal is clear: to immortalize the story of the glory of railways in Banjarnegara, which led to the creation of an article titled "The Development and Utilization of the Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara Railway Line during the Dutch Colonial Period, 1898-1942."

METHOD

This study uses the historical method. The historical method is a process of examining the accuracy of records and relics from the past, critically analyzing them, and synthesizing them into a credible historical narrative (Hugiono & Perwantoro, 1987:40). The historical method was used because the object of this study was social events in the past. The benefits of using the historical method are that it involves a process of critically investigating the circumstances, developments, and experiences of the past, and carefully considering the validity of historical sources (Rahman, 2017:131). Based on this, the historical method is the appropriate method because it involves stages of testing to make information from the past scientifically credible. The historical method is a way or technique of reconstructing past events through four stages of work, namely heuristics, verification, interpretation, and historiography (Hamid, 2011:43). Meanwhile, Kuntowijoyo adds that the selection of topics must be done before the four stages of the historical research method are carried out (Kuntowijoyo, 2013: 64). Based on this, the stages of the historical method begin with the selection of topics, followed by the four other stages: heuristics, verification, interpretation, and historiography.

The selection of a topic is the initial stage undertaken by historical researchers to determine what topic will be studied. The topic selected for this study is the history of railways in Banjarnegara. Kuntowijoyo (2013:70) states that the selection of a topic consists of two choices, namely emotional closeness and intellectual closeness. This research leans more towards intellectual affinity because there is not much written about the history of local railways in Banjarnegara. Most of the existing references are about railways in the Banyumas Residency, so writing about railways in Banjarnegara is an effort to add to the references on railways in Indonesia. The next stage is heuristics. At this stage, a historical researcher collects historical sources that will be used to complete the research. Heuristics is a stage that must be carried out by a researcher by exploring, searching, and collecting relevant sources to be studied, whether they are physical or oral sources (Ravico, et al., 2023:121). The historical sources collected at this stage came from various places, such as the UMP History Education Study Program Laboratory, KITLV, and several colleagues who had conducted research related to railways. Some of the sources obtained included historical photographs, journals, railway records, and history books discussing railways.

Verification is the next stage in this research. After determining the topic and sources to be collected, the next stage is verification, or historical criticism, or source validity (Herlina, 2020:46). Researchers check the authenticity of sources through external criticism and the credibility of sources through internal criticism (Abdurrahman, 2019:108). This checking is carried out on important sources, both primary and secondary. For example, checks are carried out on the SDS railway map passing through the Banjarnegara region, published by the Broek en Van Gheel printing factory from KITLV. This ensures that the sources used are authentic in terms of the year of publication and the data required for the research. If the data does not match, the sources obtained from the heuristic stage will be eliminated. The next stage is interpretation. Prasetyo (2020:64) states that interpretation is the process of analyzing and interpreting data. Data selected through the source criticism stage is examined at this stage. Researchers interpret the data so that it can be incorporated into the final stage of the research. Data in the form of images, photos, and tables are broken down into readable data. After that, the historiography stage begins. Historiography is the presentation of research data interpretation in the form of writing or research reports (Abdullah, 2019:21). Historiography is an important part of historical research because researchers present their research results for consumption by the wider community. Therefore, it requires carefulness and maturity in translating historical data that has been processed into a historical story that is easy for the general public to understand. In this study,

DEVELOPMENT AND UTILIZATION OF THE PURWAREJA KLAMPOK-BANJARNEGARA RAILWAY LINE DURING THE DUTCH COLONIAL PERIOD, 1898-1942

Iskandar et al

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the Dutch colonial period, industrial development in Banyumas experienced growth, requiring more adequate transportation facilities. This prompted the colonial government to actively build facilities to connect every district under the Banyumas Residency. Since the Dutch occupied Banyumas in 1830, the residency area has undergone many changes. By 1930, the Banyumas Residency consisted of Banyumas, Cilacap, Purbalingga, and Banjarnegara (Nurwanti, Harnoko, & Larasati, 2015:15). These areas were difficult to access due to their location in hilly and valley regions. The colonial government began to build infrastructure such as roads, bridges, and a canal known as the Kaliyasa Canal to connect the Serayu River with the coast of Cilacap (Sukardi, 2014:95). Cilacap was an important area for the Banyumas Residency because it was a port that could be used as an export route for goods produced by industries in Banyumas.

Transportation in Banyumas continued to develop in line with the development carried out by the Dutch Colonial government. On April 24, 1894, a decree by the Queen of the Netherlands finally ratified the draft deed of establishment of *NV Serajoedal Stoomtram Maatschappij* (SDS), and NV SDS was officially inaugurated on April 30, 1894 (Basundoro, 2018:63). SDS became a private company that built railway lines in the Banyumas region (Prayogo, Prabowo, & Radityo, 2022:17). Since then, railway lines have been opened and entered the Banyumas region. The lines built by SDS were short. The line covered almost the entire Banyumas Residency, namely the Maos-Purbalingga and Banjarsari-Wonosobo lines (Subarkah, 1992:17). The SDS line was connected to the line operated by the *Staatssoprwegen* (SS) airline company, which operated on the west side or SS Westerlijnen in the Maos area.

The railway line built by SDS runs through the Banjarnegara Regency, namely the Purwareja Klampok to Banjarnegara line. This line is the longest line built by SDS, covering a distance of 30 km (Priyadi, 2019). The construction of the railway line was carried out in stages. Basundoro (2008:65) states that construction began in May 1895 in stages, covering Maos-Purwokerto-Sokaraja-Banjarsari-Purwareja-Banjarnegara. The line built between Purwareja Klampok and Banjarnegara runs almost entirely parallel to the Serayu River, stretching from west to east. The line through Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara starts from Purwareja Klampok, Gandulekor, Bantar, Mandiraja, Purwonegoro, Gumiwang, Binorong, Mantrianom, Pucang, and ends in Banjarnegara. After three years of construction, the Purwareja Klampok to Banjarnegara line was officially opened on May 18, 1898 (Basundoro, 2008:66).

Figure 1. Map of the Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara railway line.
Source: (Broek and van Gheel, 1913)

Utilization of the railway line

The construction of the railway line became one of the supporting accesses for the Dutch Colonial government's industry. This included the line that entered the Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara area. This would facilitate the transportation of goods from the interior of Banjarnegara to Banyumas and to the port in Cilacap. In addition to being used to transport industrial goods that developed during the Dutch colonial period, railways were also used as public transportation. Before the advent of railways, transportation in the Banyumas Residency still relied on traditional means of transportation such as carts, horse-drawn carriages, and even carrying goods on stretchers. According to the *Statistieke opgaven der Residentie Banjoemaas* in 1831, the number of traditional means of transportation in Banyumas was 550 ox carts, 2,013 cow carts, and 1,239 horse-drawn carts (Basundoro, 2019:41).

DEVELOPMENT AND UTILIZATION OF THE PURWAREJA KLAMPOK-BANJARNEGARA RAILWAY LINE DURING THE DUTCH COLONIAL PERIOD, 1898-1942

Iskandar et al

The use of traditional transportation will complicate the transportation of goods from the state banjar to other areas in the Banyumas Residency. The first use of the Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara railway line was, of course, for industrial commodities produced in the Purwareja Klampok and Banjarnegara areas, all the way to Wonosobo. The main industrial commodity there was sugar. Sugar was very popular in the 19th century. Many sugar factories were built in the Dutch East Indies in the 1800s, reaching their peak in the 1930s with a production capacity of 3 million tons/year (Nugroho, Yuliasuti, Rukayah, Nugroho, & Cahyono, 2020:120). This large amount indicates that sugar transportation required adequate transportation such as railways. This was also the reason behind the introduction of the railway line in Banjarnegara because there was a Klampok Factory there.

Since the Klampok Sugar Factory was established in 1889, it has been widely recognized that an adequate transportation system is an urgent necessity (Basundoro, 2019:126). Before the railway network was built, in 1890 the Klampok Sugar Factory shipped 1,190 tons of sugar via the Serayu River to the port of Cilacap (Basundoro, 2008:64). This shipment was time-consuming and risky due to the unstable river route. The existence of the railway line provided advantages for sugar plantations and sugar factories in Banjarnegara. In addition to faster travel times, the railroad provided a guarantee of route stability. The Klampok Sugar Factory ceased operations in 1933 and was liquidated in 1936 (Wicaksono, 2021). This occurred due to the Malaise crisis. The Malaise crisis had a severe impact on Dutch plantations, causing them to collapse completely, and the production levels of plantations managed by the colonial government declined drastically (Perdana, Susanto, & Ekwandari, 2019: 240). This crisis also contributed to the cessation of sugar transportation via the SDS Line from the Klampok sugar factory.

Figure 2. The railroad tracks crossing the Klampok Sugar Factory in 1920

Source: (KITLV, 1920)

Commodities transported via the Purwareja-Klampok route to Banjarnegara, apart from sugar, were plantation goods originating from Wonosobo. The Wonosobo region is a producer of tea, cinchona, and tobacco, so fast transportation is needed to transport these commodities to Batavia for export (Novia, Sodiq, & Purnomo, 2015:26). Since the 1917 railway network reached Wonosobo, tobacco transportation, which previously passed through Pekalongan, switched to using the railroad (Basundoro, 2019:147). The Pekalongan route, which passed through hills, was too dangerous and risky, so the alternative chosen was the railway line connecting the Wonosobo region to the industrial goods delivery route to Banyumas and other cities. Freight transportation via the railway line continued to increase in the following years until it declined during the economic crisis after World War I. All industrial sectors became sluggish, as did the plantation industry. Secondly, the Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara railway line is used to transport goods needed by the community. Daily necessities will certainly be more easily delivered to the community if they are sent via the railway line. Sukardi (2014: 97) states that goods transported by train can be divided into two categories, namely goods needed in Banyumas and goods leaving the Banyumas Residency. Goods needed in Banyumas include household appliances, cement, and building materials, while goods transported from Banyumas include industrial products for export, such as tobacco and sugar. Basundoro (2019:195)

also adds that since the railway line reached Banjarnegara, goods transported by rail were not only from sugar factories but also goods needed by the wider community.

Table 1. Goods transported by rail in the Banyumas Residency

Goods transported to the Banyumas Residency	Goods transported from the Banyumas Residency
Paint and paint materials, beverages, sugar sacks, household goods, machinery and metal goods, furniture and household tools, lubricating oil, kerosene, fertilizer, carts/carts, coal, sugar cane, sugar cane seeds, fish, grease (lubricant), candles, iron and other metals, soap, salt, flour, lime, machinery, paper, thread, matches, ammunition, tar and asphalt, gasoline, limestone, sand, and animal feed	Pottery, copra, roof tiles, gambier, vegetables and fruit, resin, firewood, timber, leather, soybeans, cinchona bark, coffee, oil cake, horses and other livestock, rice, rattan, sugar, tobacco, tea, woven goods, ice, charcoal, cotton, cane syrup, waste, indigo, spices, ornamental plants, cassava, poultry, potatoes, sesame, incense, and husks

Source: (Basundoro, 2019:195-196)

The goods brought in were items needed by the community at that time, including Europeans living in the Banyumas Residency. Meanwhile, the goods brought out were mostly agricultural products from the interior of Banjarnegara and Wonosobo that were needed in Banyumas and for export. The third use of railways is as a mode of transportation for people who want to travel. Trains are used as a substitute for traditional modes of transportation such as horse-drawn carts, pedati, sado, carts, and walking. Rail transportation is a convenient and fast means of travel. Since the 1900s, trains have become the preferred mode of transportation because the cost of traveling by train is cheaper than other existing modes of transportation (Tim Telaga Bakti Nusantara, 1997:84). This condition also occurs in the SDS railway line area that passes through Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara. This railway line is used by passengers from all walks of life, but it is mostly used by middle-class traders traveling to Purwokerto and Wonosobo (Novita, Sodik, & Purnomo, 2015:27). Trains have several carriages, so they have a larger capacity. Traders use it to carry their goods. This is considered more effective than using conventional transportation, which is slow and more expensive.

Table 2 shows the number of passengers boarding trains at stations or stops between Purwareja Klampok and Banjarnegara.

Table 2. Number of train passengers from stations passed by the SDS railway line between Purwareja Klampok and Banjarnegara

No	Train station	Year and Number of Passengers				
		1920	1921	1922	1923	1924
1	Purwareja	227.680	37.069	176.636	21.498	134.272
2	Gandulekor	40.798	42.698	30.464	7.112	18.764.
3	Bantar	11.834	34.718	8.512	82.548	4.474
4	Mandiraja	132.437	216.210	96.954	7.112	72.659
5	Purwanegara	142.488	40.957	101.719	82.549	79.723
6	Gumiwang	33.218	12.441	22.599	91.689	17.312
7	Pasar Binorong	49.554	123.847	35.844	20.449	21.762
8	Mantrianom	192.337	127.306	141.163	30.873	101.804
9	Pucang	46.341	26.644	34.614	116.788	24.404
10	Wangon	21.591	42.554	15.748	28.213	7.652
11	Banjarnegara	418.479	169.418	320.447	12.107	224.325
Jumlah		1.316.757	873.862	857.700	411.284	707.151

Source: (Basundoro, 2019:189)

Utilization of railway lines at the end of Dutch colonial rule

Towards the end of Dutch rule in the Dutch East Indies, the economy experienced a severe depression. This was caused by the global economic crisis that affected various economic sectors around the world. The Great

DEVELOPMENT AND UTILIZATION OF THE PURWAREJA KLAMPOK-BANJARNEGARA RAILWAY LINE DURING THE DUTCH COLONIAL PERIOD, 1898-1942

Iskandar et al

Depression was an event that caused a dramatic decline in economic levels throughout the world, beginning in 1929 (Fathoni, 2019). This crisis affected all European countries. Its impact also affected the colonies that were the breadbasket for European countries. The collapse of the economies of European countries led to a decline in their interest in colonial plantation products, including those from the Dutch East Indies (Siswoyo, Ekwandari, & Wakidi, 2017). This led to a decrease in the intensity of plantation product exports. Indonesia (the Dutch East Indies) was highly dependent on exports, especially petroleum and agricultural products (Ricklefs, 2010:399). When the export sector experienced a deadlock, the economy became sluggish and the wheels of industry slowly began to experience a decline in production and activity.

The railway sector was also affected by this crisis. The transportation of plantation products, which initially relied heavily on railways, gradually declined due to a decrease in export demand. The transportation of plantation products on the Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara line was also affected by this crisis. This was exacerbated by the closure of several sugar factories (PG) in Banyumas in 1933, such as PG Kalibagor, PG Klampok, PG Purwokerto, PG Sumpiuh, and PG Bojong (Novita, Sodiq, & Purnomo, 2015:28). The closure of these factories certainly had a significant impact on SDS's revenue as a railway operator in Banyumas. Other freight transport sectors also experienced a decline, as can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Data on freight transportation on the Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara railway line (in tons)

Station	1930		1931		1932		1933	
	send	receive	send	receive	send	receive	send	receive
Purwareja	38.387	25.198	28.727	30.763	37.605	3.287	6.464	1.250
Gandulekor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bantar	-	--	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mandiraja	1.146	266	709	222	1.065	111	150	34
Purwanegara	423	512	751	151	148	69	11	49
Gumiwang	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pasar Binorong	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mantrianom	821	315	475	114	597	58	645	45
Pucang	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wangon	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Banjarnegara	9363	7003	8118	5394	4964	4109	3639	3215
Jumlah	50414	33295	38780	36664	44379	7634	10909	4593

Source: (Basundoro, 2019:199-200)

Table 3 shows a decline in freight transport from 1930 to 1933 when the number of goods sent and received is added up. The most severe decline occurred in 1933. This coincided with the closure of railway companies in the Banyumas Regency. The year 1933 was the worst year for SDS because its income was very low (Basundoro, 2019:201). Traffic passing through Banjarnegara also decreased, both in terms of goods and passengers. After reaching its lowest point in 1933, the world economy began to improve, including in the Dutch colonies, namely the Dutch East Indies. Gradually, economic activity in the Banyumas Residency began to increase again. Railway operations on the SDS line also began to increase again. In 1936, the Kalibagor Sugar Factory resumed operations, although other sugar factories, including the Klampok Sugar Factory, were no longer open and ceased operations permanently (Basundoro, 2019: 201). Nevertheless, railway activities in Banjarnegara continued and slowly recovered. A significant change occurred in 1942. History changed when Japan succeeded in conquering the Dutch East Indies. The Banyumas Residency did not escape Japanese control, including important sectors such as railways. From that moment on, all Dutch East Indies railway lines were under the control of the Japanese military government. This control marked the end of railway operations by Dutch East Indies companies, including SDS in the Banyumas Residency.

CONCLUSION

The Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara railway line is connected to other railway lines in the Banyumas Regency. This railway line connects Maos, Banyumas, Purbalingga, and Wonosobo. This line was built by the private railway company *Serajoedal Stoomtram Maatschappij*, commonly abbreviated as SDS, which was established on April 30, 1894. The construction of this line mostly follows or runs parallel to the Serayu River. The

DEVELOPMENT AND UTILIZATION OF THE PURWAREJA KLAMPOK-BANJARNEGARA RAILWAY LINE DURING THE DUTCH COLONIAL PERIOD, 1898-1942

Iskandar et al

construction of the SDS line in Banyumas aimed to meet the transportation needs in the interior of Banyumas. Construction of the SDS line began in 1895. Construction was carried out in stages, covering Maos-Purwokerto-Sokaraja-Banjarsari-Purwareja-Banjarnegara. The construction of this line also passed through sugar factories in the Residency, with the aim of facilitating the transportation of sugar industry products, which had begun to increase since the 19th century. The Purwareja-Klampok line, the longest section of the SDS Project at 30 km, was completed three years later in 1898. This line was officially opened for transportation on May 18, 1898. The utilization of the Purwareja Klampo-Banjarnegara railway line played an important role in the socio-economic life of the community and the Dutch colonial government's industry at that time. First, this line was used to transport industrial goods such as sugar, tobacco, and other industrial products. The railway line connecting sugar factories in the Banyumas Residency provided benefits for sugar factory companies at that time by facilitating the transportation of goods to ports for export purposes. Similarly, the tobacco industry, which previously passed through Pekalongan, shifted to using rail transport to Wonosobo after the railway line was built. Tobacco was then transported by train to the port of Cilacap and shipped to Batavia.

Secondly, trains were used to transport daily necessities for communities in the interior of the Banyumas Residency and outside of it. The goods brought in were those needed by the community at that time, including Europeans living in the Banyumas Residency. Meanwhile, the goods transported out were mostly agricultural products from the interior of Banjarnegara and Wonosobo that were needed in Banyumas or for export. Rail transportation facilitated the transport of these goods because it had a larger transport capacity than conventional transportation. Third, it serves as a means of passenger transportation. Trains are a comfortable and fast means of transportation. Since the 1900s, trains have been the preferred mode of transportation because the cost of traveling by train is cheaper than other existing modes of transportation. The train that runs through Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara has never been short of passengers since it was first inaugurated. This route, which takes people to various areas in Banyumas, has been able to replace horse-drawn carts, sado, and traditional modes of transportation that took longer to travel. The existence of trains was the solution to transportation problems during the Dutch colonial period. All aspects, such as industry, society, and the economy, benefited from the presence of the railroad that entered the Banjarnegara area at that time.

The development of railways in the Banyumas Residency since its inception showed significant improvement, including on the Purwareja Klampok-Banjarnegara line. This line was originally one of the busiest routes for both freight and passenger traffic, reaching its peak activity before 1929. However, after that year, railway activities in Banyumas and throughout the Dutch East Indies declined due to the global economic crisis known as the Malaise. The plantation industry, especially sugar and coffee, experienced a decline in production due to falling export demand. European countries, which were the main export destinations, were hit by a crisis that impacted the agricultural and plantation sectors in the colonies, including the Dutch East Indies. The decline in export shipments had a direct impact on the decline in rail transport volume, including on the SDS line in Purwareja Klampok. In fact, the only sugar factory on that line, the Klampok Sugar Factory, was also closed in 1933. Although the industrial sector experienced a decline, railway operations continued, albeit not as busy as before. After the crisis ended, economic conditions began to recover. One of the sugar factories in Banyumas, namely the Kalibagor Sugar Factory, was reactivated, but not the Klampok Sugar Factory, which never resumed operations permanently. Economic activity via the railway continued until the arrival of the Japanese, who took control of the entire Dutch East Indies in 1942. From that point on, the Dutch-built railway lines were taken over by the Japanese occupation government, marking the end of their operation by the Dutch colonial government.

Based on the results of research on the history of railways in Banjarnegara, it can be concluded that the use of railway lines in the Banjarnegara region is an important and urgent need. Therefore, the government's efforts to revitalize or reactivate the Purworejo Klampok-Banjarnegara railway line are strategic and appropriate steps. The existence of this railway line not only improves the accessibility and effectiveness of transportation, but also has the potential to have a positive impact on the economic growth of the local community. In addition, the development of more equitable transportation infrastructure is expected to accelerate regional development and provide benefits equivalent to those enjoyed by other regions on the island of Java

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, A. F. (2019). Perempuan Indonesia Sampai Awal Abad ke-20. *Entitia: Jurnal Pendidikan Ilmu Pengetahuan Sosial dan Ilmu-Ilmu Sosial Vol 1 No 1*, 20-28 <https://doi.org/10.19105/ejps.v1i1.2939>.
- Abdurrahman, D. (2019). *Metodologi Penelitian Sejarah Islam*. Yogyakarta: Ombak.
- Arkaan, H. E., Yunianto, T., & Kurniawan, D. A. (2022). Pembangunan Transportasi Kereta Api dan pengaruhnya Terhadap Ekologi Kota Surakarta 1864-1942. *Jurnal Candi Vol 22 No 1*, 95-111 <https://jurnal.uns.ac.id/candi/article/view/72328/40032>.
- Basundoro, P. (2008). Dinamika Pengangkutan di Banyumas Pada Era Modernisasi Transportasi pada Awal Abad Ke-20. *Humaniora Vol. 20 No. 1*, 63-74.
- Basundoro, P. (2019). *Arkeologi Transportasi: Prespektif Ekonomi dan Kewilayahan Karesidenan Banyumas 1830-1940an*. Surabaya: Airlangga Press.
- Broek en van Gheel. (1913). *Algemene overzichtskaart, D E 46,9*. Diambil kembali dari Leiden University Libraries: Digital Collections: <http://hdl.handle.net/1887.1/item:814436> diakses pada 16 November 2025
- Fathoni, R. S. (2019). *Krisis Malaise dan Dampaknya terhadap Hindia Belanda Baca selengkapnya di artikel "Krisis Malaise dan Dampaknya terhadap Hindia Belanda*. Diambil kembali dari Wawasan Sejarah: <https://wawasansejarah.com/krisis-malaise-hindia-belanda/> diakses pada 25 November 2025
- Hamid, A. R. (2011). *Pengantar Ilmu Sejarah*. Yogyakarta: Ombak.
- Herlina, N. (2020). *Metode Sejarah*. Bandung: Satya Historika.
- Hugiono, & Perwantoro, P. k. (1987). *Pengantar Ilmu Sejarah*. Jakarta : Bina Aksara.
- Kementrian Perhubungan. (2020). *Buku Informasi Perkeretaapian*. Jakarta: Direktorat Jendral Perkeretaapian.
- KITLV. (1920). *Suikerfabriek Klampok ten oosten van Banjoemas*. Diambil kembali dari Leiden University Libraries: Digital Collections: <http://hdl.handle.net/1887.1/item:784179> diakses pada 19 November 2025
- Kuntowijoyo. (2013). *Pengantar Ilmu Sejarah*. Yogyakarta: Tiara Wacana.
- Novita, F., Sodik, i., & Purnomo, A. (2015). Perkeretaapian di Wonosobo 1917-1942. *Journal Of Indonesian History Vol 4 No 1*, 23-31 <http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jih>.
- Nugroho, P. S., Yulastuti, n., Rukayah, R. S., Nugroho, R., & Cahyono, U. j. (2020). Identifikasi Pabrik Gula Sebagai Industrial Heritage Di Jawa. *Arsitektura : Jurnal Ilmu Arsitektur dan Lingkungan Binaan, Vol. 18 (1)*, 119-128 <https://doi.org/10.20961/arst.v18i1.37936>.
- Nurwanti, Y. H., Harnoko, D., & Larasati, T. A. (2015). *Sejarah Perkembangan Kebudayaan dan Ekonomi di Banyumas masa Gandasubrata Tahun 1913-1942*. Yogyakarta: Balai Pelestarian Nilai Budaya.
- Perdana, Y., Susanto, H., & Ekwandari, Y. S. (2019). Dinamika Industri Gula Sejak Cultuurstelsel Hingga Krisis Malaise Tahun 1830 – 1929. *HISTORIA: Jurnal Program Studi Pendidikan Sejarah VVol 7 No 2*, 227-242 <http://dx.doi.org/10.24127/hj.v7i2.2117>.
- Prasetyo, Y. (2020). Dari Pikulan ke Kelontong: Tionghoa dan Toko Kelontong Yogyakarta 1900 –1942. *Entitia: Jurnal Pendidikan Ilmu Pengetahuan Sosial dan Ilmu-Ilmu Sosial Vol 2 No 1*, 63-78.
- Prayogo, Y. B., Prabowo, Y. S., & Radityo, D. (2022). *Kereta Api Indonesia: Seputar Lokomotif Uap*. Yogyakarta: Jogja Bangkit Publisher.
- Priyadi, S. (2019). *Sejarah Kota Purwakerto (Purwokerto) (1832-2018)*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.
- Rahman, F. (2017). Menimbang Sejarah sebagai Landasan Kajian Ilmiah: ebuah Wacana Pemikiran dalam Metode Ilmiah. *El-Banat: Jurnal Pemikiran dan Pendidikan Islam Vol 7 No 1*, 128-150 <https://doi.org/10.54180/elbanat.2017.7.1.128-150>.
- Ravico, Rochmiatun, E., Sustianingsih, I. M., Susetyo, B., & Ramadhona, N. (2023). Implementasi Heuristik dalam Penelitian Sejarah Bagi Mahasiswa. *Chronologia Vol 4 No 3*, 118-128 <https://www.doi.org/10.22236/jhe.v4i3.11089>.
- Siswoyo, T., Ekwandari, Y. S., & Wakidi. (2017). Pengaruh Malaise Terhadap Perkebunan Kolonial di Hindia Belanda Tahun 1930-1940. *Pesagi: Jurnal Pendidikan dan Penelitian Sejarah Vol 5 No 9*, <https://jips.fkip.unila.ac.id/index.php/PES/article/view/14588/pdf>.
- Soekendro, H. (2024). *Rel KA Purwokerto-Wonosobo Dibangun 2030, Lewati 16 Stasiun dan Butuh Dana Rp8,3 Triliun*. Diambil kembali dari Suaramerdeka.com: <https://www.suaramerdeka.com/jawa-tengah/0413257102/rel-ka-purwokerto-wonosobo-dibangun-2030-lewati-16-stasiun-dan-butuh-dana-rp83-triliun>
- Subarkah, I. (1992). *Sekilas 125 Tahun Kereta Api Kita 1867-1992*. Bandung: Integritas.
- Sukardi, T. (2014). *Tanam Paksa di Banyumas: Kajian mengenai Sistem, Pelaksanaan, dan Dampak Sosial Ekonomi*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.

DEVELOPMENT AND UTILIZATION OF THE PURWAREJA KLAMPOK-BANJARNEGARA RAILWAY LINE DURING THE DUTCH COLONIAL PERIOD, 1898-1942

Iskandar et al

Tim telaga Bakti Nusantara. (1997). *Sejarah Perkeretaapian Indonesia Jilid I*. Bandung: CV. Angkasa.

Wicaksono, J. (2021, Ferbruari 15). *Pabrik Gula KLampok*. Diambil kembali dari Web Blog Sejarah Lokal Banyumas Raya: <https://www.banjoemas.com/2010/10/suikerfabriek-klampok.html> diakses pada 23 November 2025